

PSYCHOLOGICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL ASPECTS OF WRITING A MUSICAL DICTATION - AS THE BASIS OF MODERN METHODOLOGY OF MUSIC PEDAGOGY.

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Introduction:

The main task of musical dictation is the formation of such psychological processes as logical and abstract thinking, attention, attitude, musical memory, which develop such auditory abilities as speed of memorization reaction, competent fixation of musical notation.

Many students can not cope with writing dictation because of fear, that is, for psychological reasons, and it is as a result of this that a solfejst teacher needs to know the laws of psychological perception of music in order to correctly organize differentiated management of this process.

The psychology of musical dictation perception consists of several components:

Let's look at them in more detail. For a person's perception of musical material (dictation), first of all, a psychological attitude is necessary, which is given by the teacher for active and purposeful listening, which mobilizes the intellectual and volitional qualities of the student.

The dictation must have highly artistic qualities. Beautiful and interesting music creates positive emotions, which, combined with the structural complexity of the music, attract the student's attention even more and contribute to the effectiveness of the memorization process. Self-perception of dictation is classified according to the principle of gradual complication of square symmetrical simple constructions to more complex, melodically expanded ones, which will certainly reflect all the knowledge and skills gained in the course of solfeggio, music theory, harmony.

A very important function in writing dictation is the organization of the process of listening perception itself. Therefore, we consider musical dictation as the most effective method of developing and regulating auditory activity. And the teacher acts as the organizer of this process, which creates students' psychological attitude to perception.

The installation performs a defining function in organizational activities and includes::

- a) the brain's readiness for certain activities,

- b) the existence of a goal and need for the activity,
- c) the relationship of perception with existing experience.

These qualities of the attitude are transformed into efficiency and pass into the effectiveness of perception. And the effectiveness in writing a musical dictation is the implementation of an artistic and stylistic image, its syntactic and intonation components.

Types of dictation should be aimed at optimizing the memorization process, where everyone performs their own pedagogical task and therefore in the learning process should not be limited to just a few types, but apply in practice all the variety of them. Let's denote the main types of dictation:

1. Singalongs
2. voice
3. Rhythmic
4. Oral
5. Analytical services
6. Creative projects
7. Timbre settings

The most effective types are analytical, where with the help of a teacher, students learn to determine the structure, syntactic features of the palm-tone plan, rhythmic figures, characteristic intonation turns and jumps, range, and only then start recording. Such dictations, combined with oral and rhythmic ones, contribute to the effectiveness of the memorization process. Timbre and creative varieties are psychologically accessible and interesting for the older audience of students who have writing skills and have sufficient experience in writing dictation.

The ability to combine different types of musical dictation in pedagogical practice contributes to the effectiveness of memorizing and grouping information in specific blocks and constructions, and, finally, as a result, writing dictation from memory, which means that it is covered by the ear in all its integrity and is a synthesis of the teacher's musical goals and psychological efforts and skills of the student.

The musical dictation in the course "Solfeggio" reflects as a "litmus test" the musical-auditory, logical, psychological, as well as cognitive qualities of the student, revealing all facets of his talent, skills and acquired knowledge in the field of music-theoretical disciplines, and taking into account the psychological and pedagogical aspects allows the teacher and students to demonstrate the

effectiveness of modern teaching methods in this field. educational process of the Republican Specialized Music School named after V. Uspensky.

